

Neutrix Product of Three Distributions Using Fractional Differentiation

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Abstract - Product of two or more distributions is not defined in general. In this paper, using fractional differentiations the product of three distributions is defined on neutrix limit and then verified the result by giving some examples. Specially product of distributions is taken with the $\delta^{(\alpha)}(x)$, where α is a positive fractional number.

Keywords – Neutrix limit, fractional- differential, sequence, function.

1. Introduction: J.G. Vander Corput [3] defined the neutrix \mathcal{N} as a commutative additive group of functions $v(\xi)$ defined on a domain \mathcal{N}' with values in \mathcal{N}'' , an additive group. The functions in \mathcal{N} are called negligible functions if for some v in \mathcal{N} , $v(\xi) = \gamma$ for all ξ in \mathcal{N}' , and $\gamma = 0$. Now let \mathcal{N}' be a set contained in a topological space with a limit point c which does not belong to \mathcal{N}' . If $f(\xi)$ is a function defined on \mathcal{N}' with values in \mathcal{N}'' and it is possible to find a constant β such that $f(\xi) - \beta$ is negligible in \mathcal{N} , then β is called the Neutrix limit or N -limit off f as ξ tends to c and we write

$$N - \lim_{\xi \rightarrow c} f(\xi) = \beta$$

where β must be unique, if it exists.

The use of neutrix calculus has turned has demonstrated itself as very helpful in the investigation of singular expressions and distribution products. Early contributions concerning the product of distributions, generalized functions, and fractional differentiation provided the basic analytical foundation for this theory [1,2,4,5]. Subsequently, the neutrix products of two and three distributions were studied in detail in [9, 10], and related properties of the Dirac delta function were discussed in [11]. More recent investigations involving generalized functions, commutative and non-commutative neutrix products, ultra-distributions, asymptotic analysis, and fractional-operator-based methods have further expanded this theory [12-17]. These developments provide the motivation for the present work.

Fisher [4] defined the neutrix product of two distributions as follows -

Definition (1.1): Let f and g be arbitrary distributions and let

$$g_n = g * \delta_n = \int_{-\frac{1}{n}}^{\frac{1}{n}} g(x-t)\delta_n(t)dt,$$

for $n = 1,2,3, \dots$, where $\{\delta_n\}$ converges to dirac-delta distribution δ , and $\delta_n(x) = n\rho(nx)$, ρ

is an infinitely differentiable function having the properties -

- (i) $\rho(x) = 0$ for $|x| \geq 1$
- (ii) $\rho(x) \geq 0$
- (iii) $\rho(x) = \rho(-x)$
- (iv) $\int_{-1}^1 \rho(x) dx = 1,$

Neutrix product of f and g is $f \circ g$ exists and equal to a distribution h if

$$N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle f g_n, \phi \rangle = N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle f, g_n \phi \rangle = \langle h, \phi \rangle,$$

for all test functions $\phi \in K$, with support contained in the interval (a, b) , where \mathcal{N} is the Neutrix having domain $\mathcal{N}' = \{1, 2, \dots, n, \dots\}$ and range \mathcal{N}'' of the real numbers with negligible functions

$$n^\lambda \ln^{r-1} n, \ln^r n,$$

for $\lambda > 0$, and $r = 1, 2, \dots$ and all functions $f(n)$ for which $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(n) = 0$.

Riemann - Liouville and Wéyl-fractional integral operators are defined in [1] for $Re\alpha > 0$ as -

$$(I^\alpha f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt,$$

$$\text{and } (K^\alpha f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^\infty (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt$$

In [7. p.658] the fractional differential operator is defined as -

$$I^\alpha f = D^\alpha f, \tag{1.1}$$

$$K^\alpha f = (-1)^\alpha D^\alpha f, \tag{1.2}$$

These operators are adjoint, i.e.

$$\langle I^{-\alpha} f, \phi \rangle = \langle f, K^{-\alpha} \phi \rangle \tag{1.3}$$

$$\text{and } \langle K^{-\alpha} f, \phi \rangle = \langle f, I^{-\alpha} \phi \rangle \tag{1.4}$$

In the present paper we will obtain an expression for the Neutrix product of three distributions and prove the distributive law by using fractional differentiation. At the end will also give some examples to use our results.

2. This section is devoted in obtaining an expression for the Neutrix product of three distributions and proving the distributive laws.

Theorem (2.1) : If f, g and h are arbitrary distributions such that $f = I^{-\alpha}F$ with $F \in L^{p_1}(a, b), g^{(r)}$ and $h^{(r)}$ are ordinary summable functions belonging to $L^{p_2}(a, b)$ and $L^{p_3}(a, b)$ respectively with $1/p_1 + 1/p_2 + 1/p_3 = 1$ and if the neutrix product $(f \circ g) \circ h$ exists on (a, b) then we have

$$(f \circ g) \circ h = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \circ (g^{(r-i)} \circ h^{(i)})\}$$

Proof: For arbitrary $\phi \in K$, we have by definition (1.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle (f \circ g) \circ h, \phi \rangle &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \{ (f \circ g) h_n, \phi \} \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle f g_n, h_n \phi \rangle \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle f, (g_n h_n) \phi \rangle \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle (I^{-\alpha}F)(g_n h_n), \phi \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\langle \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \cdot D^r(g_n h_n)\}, \phi \right\rangle$$

[by [10]]

$$= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r \langle I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \cdot D^r(g_n h_n)\}, \phi \rangle$$

$$= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r \langle F \cdot D^r(g_n h_n), K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi \rangle$$

[by(1.3)]

$$= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \langle F \cdot (D^{(r-i)} g_n D^i h_n), K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi \rangle$$

[by Leibniz rule]

$$= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \langle I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \cdot (g_n^{(r-i)} h_n^{(i)})\}, \phi \rangle$$

$$= \left\langle \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \circ (g^{(r-i)} \circ h^{(i)})\}, \phi \right\rangle$$

Thus, we have

$$(f \circ g) \circ h = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i I^{-(\alpha-r)} \{F \circ (g^{(r-i)} \circ h^{(i)})\}$$

Theorem (2.2): If f, g and h are arbitrary distributions such that $f = I^{-\alpha}F$ and $g = I^{-\alpha}G$, where F and G are ordinary summable functions and if the Neutrix product $f \circ h$ and $g \circ h$ exists then for the scalars u and v we have

$$(uf + vg) \circ h = u(f \circ h) + v(g \circ h) \quad (\text{Right distribution law})$$

Proof: For arbitrary $\phi \in K$, we have by definition (1.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \langle (uf + vg) \circ h, \phi \rangle &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle (uf + vg)h_n, \phi \rangle \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle u(I^{-\alpha}F) + v(I^{-\alpha}G), h_n \phi \rangle \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle u(I^{-\alpha}F), h_n \phi \rangle + N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle v(I^{-\alpha}G), h_n \phi \rangle \\ &\quad (\text{since } h_n \phi \text{ is again a testing function in } K) \quad (\text{by [6], p. 7}) \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u \langle (I^{-\alpha}F)h_n, \phi \rangle + N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} v \langle (I^{-\alpha}G)h_n, \phi \rangle \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u \langle fh_n, \phi \rangle + N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} v \langle gh_n, \phi \rangle \\ &= u \langle f \circ h, \phi \rangle + v \langle g \circ h, \phi \rangle \\ &= \langle u(f \circ h) + v(g \circ h), \phi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$(uf + vg) \circ h = u(f \circ h) + v(g \circ h)$$

Similarly, we can prove the left distribution law i.e.,

$$h \circ (uf + vg) = u(h \circ f) + v(h \circ g).$$

Theorem (2.3) : Let f and g be arbitrary distributions and let $f_n = f * \delta_n$, $g_n = g * \delta_n$, If the Neutrix limit of the sequence $\{f_n^{(r-i)}(x)\}$ and $\{g_n^i(x)\}$ exists in the neighbourhood of the origin for $r - i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, r$ and equal to ξ_{r-i} and η_i then the neutrix product $\delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (f \circ g)$ exists and

$$\delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (f \circ g) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r \alpha C_r {}^r C_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \delta^{(\alpha-r)}$$

Proof: For arbitrary $\phi \in K$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (f \circ g), \phi \rangle &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \delta^{(\alpha)} f_n, g_n \phi \rangle \quad (\text{by [8]}) \\ &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \delta^{(\alpha)}, (f_n g_n) \phi \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle I^{-\alpha} \delta, (f_n g_n) \phi \rangle \\
 &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \delta, K^{-\alpha} (f_n g_n) \phi \rangle \quad \text{[by (1.3)]}
 \end{aligned}$$

=

$$\begin{aligned}
 &N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \delta, \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi (f_n g_n)^{(r)} \rangle \\
 &\quad \text{[by [10] theorem (2.2)]} \\
 &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle \delta, \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi (f_n^{(r-i)} g_n^i) \rangle \\
 &\quad \text{[by Leibniz rule]} \\
 &= N - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \{K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi(0)\} \\
 &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \langle \delta, K^{-(\alpha-r)} \phi \rangle \\
 &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \langle I^{-(\alpha-r)} \delta, \phi \rangle \quad \text{[by(1.3)]} \\
 &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \langle \delta^{(\alpha-r)}, \phi \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (f \circ g) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^r (-1)^r {}^{\alpha}C_r {}^rC_i \xi_{r-i} \eta_i \delta^{(\alpha-r)}$$

3. In this section we will give some examples to use our results. For this we consider α to be a positive fractional number say $\alpha = p + q$, where p is an integer and $0 \leq q < 1$,

Example (1): From ([5], p.97) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &x_+^{\lambda} \circ x_+^{\mu} = x_+^{\lambda+\mu} \\
 &\text{for } \lambda, \mu, \lambda + \mu \neq -1, -2, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Neutrix product of $\delta^{(\alpha)}$ with x_+^r exists and we have for $\lambda + \mu = r = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p$

$$\delta^{(\alpha)}, x_+^r = \frac{(-1)^r \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2\Gamma(\alpha-r+1)} \delta^{(\alpha-r)} \quad \text{(by[10]case II)}$$

for $\lambda + \mu \neq 0, 1, 2, \dots, p$ we have

$$\delta^{(\alpha)} \circ x_+^{\lambda+\mu} = 0$$

Example (2): From ([4], p.122) we have

$$\delta^{(s+r)} \circ x_+^r = \frac{(-1)^r (s+r)!}{2s!} \delta^{(s)}$$

for $r, s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Therefore, the Neutrix product of $\delta^{(\alpha)}$ with $(\delta^{(s+r)} \circ x_+^r)$ exists and we have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (\delta^{(s+r)} \circ x_+^r) &= \delta^{(\alpha)} \cdot \left\{ \frac{(-1)^r (s+r)!}{2s!} \delta^{(s)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^r (s+r)!}{2s!} \{ \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ \delta^{(s)} \} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Example (3): Since $|x|^r = x_+^r + x_-^r$
so, the Neutrix product exists and

$$\delta^{(\alpha)} \circ |x|^r = \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ (x_+^r + x_-^r)$$

$$= \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ x_+^r + \delta^{(\alpha)} \circ x_-^r \quad [\text{by theorem (2.2)}]$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} &= \frac{(-1)^r \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2\Gamma(\alpha-r+1)} \delta^{(\alpha-r)} + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2\Gamma(\alpha-r+1)} \delta^{(\alpha-r)}, \text{ for } r = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p \\ &0, \quad \text{for } r \neq 0, 1, 2, \dots, p \end{aligned} \right. \quad (\text{by [10]})$$

$$= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha-r+1)} \delta^{(\alpha-r)} \quad , \text{ for } r = 2, 4, 6, \dots, s \\ &0 \quad , \text{ for } r \neq 2, 4, 6, \dots, s \end{aligned} \right.$$

Where $s = \begin{cases} p, & \text{if } p \text{ is even,} \\ p-1, & \text{if } p \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$

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